

**Benefits gained from dimensions of social capital: a study of software developers in
Sri Lanka**

**Wickramasinghe, V.
Weliwitigoda, P.**

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V., & Weliwitigoda, P. (2011). Benefits gained from dimensions of social capital: A study of software developers in Sri Lanka. Information Technology & People, 24(4), 393-413.

This Version is available at: doi: 10.1108/09593841111182287

Purpose- To investigate the dimensions of social capital and how these help software developers employed in offshore outsourced software development sector in Sri Lanka to gain benefits of knowledge sharing, job openings and job security, and career advancement.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey methodology was used and 105 software developers responded. Multiple regression was used for the data analysis.

Findings- Social relations, the number of networks an individual is being a member and the frequency of interaction between network members are identified as important dimensions that significantly predict knowledge sharing, job openings and job security and career advancement.

Originality/value- It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information to better understand the dimensions of social capital at the individual level that influence knowledge base and learning capabilities of the individuals and the nature of employment relationships to be adopted by the organisations. By so doing, this study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Keywords: career progression; knowledge sharing; social capital, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Social capital is broadly described as an asset embedded in relationships (Burt, 1997; Coleman, 1990; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). It is a moral resource and may depreciate with non-use (and with abuse); it does not depreciate with use (Adler and Kwon, 2002, p. 22). Therefore, social capital is a form of capital that changes as relationships and rewards change over time, and disappears when the relations cease to exist (see Leana and Van Buren, 1999). The present study investigated the dimensions of social capital and how these help employees engaged in knowledge work, in particular, software developers in offshore outsourced software development sector in

Sri Lanka, to gain benefits of knowledge sharing, job search and job security, and career advancement.

The novelty of the current study lies in several aspects. First, changes occurred in the business environment and the emergence of the knowledge economy has placed the employee at the centre of analysis (see De Backere and Rappa, 1994; Rodan and Galunic, 2004). The definitions and conceptualisations of social capital (refer Table 1) suggest that it can be conceived at an individual level (as a private good). However, the main shortcomings of previous empirical studies lay, on the one hand, that they include a limited number of social capital dimensions (e.g. general trust and membership in networks) and a limited number of benefits (e.g. knowledge transfer) in a single study (e.g. Inkpen and Tsang, 2005; Waters and Smith, 2008). Therefore, it is reasonable to analyze the dimensions of social capital and benefits that could be gained within an extended framework at the individual level. On the other hand, scholars suggest that individuals in protean careers should consider their social capital to be adaptable, self-directed, and focused on their employability (e.g. Hall, 2002). However, past research provides little empirical evidence on how individual actors engaged in knowledge work accrue social capital and how social relations enable them to pursue their desired goals (see Waters and Smith, 2008). Therefore, the current study extends the analysis of social capital by analyzing several factors, which are until recently had been studied separately, in a single study focusing on an emerging occupation in Sri Lanka – offshore software development.

Second, in connection to the above, the literature identifies software development as a key occupation to examine knowledge workers (see Scholarios and Marks, 2004). This is because, skills they possess remain highly marketable; they enjoy a considerable labour market power, with a high level of occupational identification, and they tend to move across organisations rather than thinking in terms of a long-term commitment to a single organisation (see Scholarios and Marks, 2004). However, knowledge and expertise that they possess leads to rapid obsolescence due to frequent

technological advancements, and their success is determined not just by what they know but by how fast they can learn and share their learning (Tymon and Stumpf, 2003).

Third, it is very rare to find research studies on social capital in offshore outsourced software development sector. Global offshore outsourced software development is held to be characterised by geographically dispersed workplaces and a global team of employees (Jarvenpaa and Mao, 2008; Mahnke et al., 2008). However, the details of what are the dimensions of their social capital and how social relations enable them to pursue their desired goals remain obscure.

Therefore, it is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information to better understand the dimensions of social capital at the individual level that could influence knowledge base and learning capabilities of the individuals and the nature of employment relationships to be adopted by the organisations. By so doing, this study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. The article is in four sections. The first section reviews the relevant literature. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. In the final section, conclusions on the findings are drawn, the implications of the findings are discussed, and research areas for further inquiry and understanding are presented.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

The concept of social capital

The term social capital has become one of the multi-disciplinary topics that enable much cross-fertilisation of ideas and some convergence of views (Crudeli et al., 2008; Khan, 2006). This ongoing theoretical debate on the topic has been accompanied by vast and exponentially growing literature. Beyond the general acceptance of social capital as an asset that inheres in social relations, researchers have used the term in competing and sometimes contradictory ways (see Leana and Van Buren, 1999). A short selection of social capital definitions and how it is treated in the social capital literature are presented

in Table 1. For instance, Burt (1992, p. 9) defined social capital as friends, colleagues, and more general contacts through whom individuals receive opportunities to use their financial and human capital. According to Putnam (2000) social connectedness and civic engagement (e.g., visiting neighbours, engagement in politics, membership in church-related groups and in civic and fraternal organisations) are the main features of social capital. For Lin (2001) social capital refers to “resources embedded in social networks accessed and used by actors for actions . . . and ... (an) investment by individuals in interpersonal relationships useful in the markets” (p. 25). By this definition, Lin (2001) asserted that the social structure component consists of people with varying levels of resources and authority, the opportunity component describes varying ways that people are encouraged or discouraged from accessing social capital, and the action component is the motivation that people has to be engaged in social relationships.

Social capital is treated in the literature as attributes of nations/geographic regions (Fukuyama, 1995), communities (Putnam, 1993), individual networks (Burt, 1992), firms in their interactions with other firms (Baker, 1990), and individual actors (Belliveau et al., 1996; Portes and Sensenbrenner, 1993) (refer to Table 1). For instance, Baker (1990) describes social capital as resources available to an individual as a result of his or her personal relationships. Bourdieu (1986) defines social capital as resources linked to possession of a network of relationships of mutual acquaintance. Hence, researchers differ in the level of analysis they use in describing social capital. However, regardless of whether social capital is construed as a pure group-level phenomenon or not, it is asserted that it will still have manifestations on the level of individual and individual-level measurements may facilitate group-level studies (see Lillbacka, 2006). In the current study we considered social capital as an asset individuals accrue and spend over the course of their work or career.

Take in Table 1

Social capital is also treated in the literature as a private good, public good or a combination of both (refer to Table 1). The scholars, who emphasise the public good facet of social capital, see it as an attribute of a social unit rather than as an attribute of an individual actor, where individuals benefit from its presence or suffer from its absence indirectly (e.g. Coleman 1990; Fukuyama, 1995; Putnam, 1993). Alternatively, social capital is treated as a private good where the focus is explicitly on the individual and his or her accrued social assets, such as prestige, educational credentials, and social clubs (e.g., Belliveau et al., 1996), and individual level benefits that can be gained directly by forming a particular type of social network such as career advancement (Burt 1992, 1997). This private good facet has been applied at the individual (e.g., Belliveau et al., 1996), group (e.g., Krackhardt, 1990), organisation and industry (e.g., Rottman, 2008) levels of analysis. However, the focus in terms of outcomes is always on the individual or unit level (Leana and Van Buren, 1999). Some researchers have incorporated both private good and public good approaches (e.g. Inkpen and Tsang, 2005; Leana and Van Buren, 1999). For instance, although Leana and Van Buren (1999) viewed social capital as an attribute of organisations and focused largely on the public good facet, they have also incorporated the private good facet to discuss specific dimensions, such as network ties. In the current study, we considered social capital as a private good and analyzed as an attribute of individual actors, i.e., software developers.

Dimensions of social capital

Social capital is frequently identified in terms of several dimensions (e.g. Crudeli et al., 2008; Kristiansen, 2004; Widén-Wulff and Ginman, 2004). For instance, at the individual level, social capital is often seen as an asset of an individual consisting of social relationships, trust and trustworthiness (norms) (e.g. Coleman 1990; Bourdieu 1986).

According to Lin (1999) the value of a person's social capital is determined by the qualities of his or her social network. Scholars (e.g. Kristiansen, 2004; McFadyen and Cannella, 2004) suggest several qualities of social networks. For instance, the number of social relations or the network size is identified as important, where a higher number of direct exchange partners in a network increases the amount of information, ideas, and resources in it (see Hislop, 2005; McFadyen and Cannella, 2004).

The strength of ties is also identified as an important dimension, which can be measured using a variety of criteria, such as the length of time two actors spend together, the emotional intensity between two actors, the degree of trust and acquaintance between the related persons, the frequency of interaction, and the time that the relationship has lasted (Kristiansen, 2004; McFadyen and Cannella, 2004). It is also suggested that different characters, occupying differing social positions, included in a social network create variety and increase the chances for actors to pick up new ideas and information of value (Kristiansen, 2004).

Further, trust in generalised other is also seen as a dimension of social capital (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). The underlying assumption is that generalised, diffused interpersonal trust indicates the readiness of an actor to enter into communication and cooperation with others (Adam, 2008). The literature suggests several facets of trust. For instance, some researchers (e.g. Burgoon et al., 2002) identify facets as being truthful, trustworthy, sincere, responsible, and reliable while some others (e.g. Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998) identify facets as belief in the good intent and concern of network members, belief in their capabilities, belief in their reliability, and belief in their perceived openness.

Furthermore, norms (including sanctions) are identified as required to enhance willingness and capacity to co-operate, to engage in collective action for mutual benefit, and to reduce free riding (Khan, 2006). Hence, norms reflect consensus among the actors in a system of relationships and provide a motivational basis for social exchange while felt obligations reflect the level of commitment to future activities and continued

exchange (Staber, 2006). Strong social norms and beliefs associated with a high degree of closure of the social network encourage compliance with local rules and customs and reduce the need for formal control (Adler and Kwon, 2002).

Benefits gained from dimensions of social capital

When social capital is understood as multi-dimensional in nature, and seen as a private good possessed by individual actors, there are several personal benefits that actors can gain directly from the dimensions of social capital. For instance, researchers found that social capital influences career advancement (Belliveau et al., 1996; Burt, 1992; Lin and Huang, 2005), compensation (Belliveau et al., 1996; Burt, 1997), knowledge sharing (De Backere and Rappa, 1994), and job search and job security (Bueno et al., 2004; Granovetter, 1995; Lin, 2001). The current study investigated three benefits that individuals could gain from their social capital, namely, knowledge sharing, job search and job security, and career advancement.

Knowledge sharing. Knowledge sharing refers to the mutual sharing of information between exchange partners (Wu, 2008). Access to new sources of knowledge is one of the most important direct benefits of social capital (Burt, 1997; Wu, 2008). Majority of the studies on the influence of social capital on knowledge sharing found that social capital facilitates access to broader sources of information and improves information's quality, relevance, and timeliness (Adler and Kwon, 2002). Hence, majority of the past research highlight the importance of social capital as a driver for knowledge sharing in organizations (e.g. Adler and Kwon, 2002; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). However, few previous studies have investigated the negative aspects of social capital within the organizational context (e.g. Willem and Scarbrough, 2006). Such studies found that although social capital generally tends to enhance the sharing of knowledge when social capital is seen as linked to power relations it becomes ambivalent and unpredictable with greater selectivity and bias in knowledge sharing (e.g. Willem and Scarbrough, 2006).

The studies that are optimistic on the influence of social capital on knowledge sharing found that knowledge sharing is facilitated by intensive social interactions of organisational actors (Inkpen and Tsang, 2005; Widén-Wulff and Ginman, 2004). It is also suggested that mutual trust encourages knowledge sharing by increasing the disclosure of knowledge to others and by granting others access to one's own knowledge, which in turn creates value in the exchange relationship (Dyer and Chu, 2003). Mutual trust can be a powerful source of communication and cooperation, especially under the conditions of high uncertainty in the international business environment (Jarvenpaa and Mao, 2008; Mahnke et al., 2008). Further, social norms create openness, cooperation, and willingness to engage in information exchange between geographically dispersed units in the global economy (Jarvenpaa and Mao, 2008; Mahnke et al., 2008). Furthermore, social networking facilitates knowledge sharing and task mastery among network members (Inkpen and Tsang, 2005). In the context of high-tech firms and new product development teams, social networks help actors to gain access to routine information as well as complex knowledge (de Janasz and Forret, 2008).

On the basis of our reading of the above reviewed literature that indicates dimensions of social capital predict personal benefits that individuals can gain directly from their social capital, and preliminary investigations made by us about software developers in offshore outsourced software development firms in Sri Lanka, it is hypothesised that the dimensions of social capital (refer to the section on *measures*) will influence the level of knowledge sharing. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 1: Dimensions of social capital will have a significant positive effect on knowledge sharing.

Job search and job security. Scholars address the influence of social capital on employees and job seekers at two facets. First, there are advantages and incentives for professionals, particularly software developers, to move from one employer to another

rather than relying on the promotion within the internal labour market of a single firm (see Scholarios and Marks, 2004). In this context, social relations help actors to search for and secure employment opportunities (Burt, 1992; Forret and Dougherty, 2004; Lin, 2001), to gain access to needed information or resources, and to obtain guidance, sponsorship, and social support (de Janasz and Forret, 2008). For instance, participating in community and voluntary activities is helpful in the job search and the determination of wages (de Janasz and Forret, 2008). In this regard, Granovetter (1995) found that acquaintances are more helpful than close friends for finding jobs because acquaintances are a source of more unique information while close friends tend to know about the same job openings. Although many studies highlighted the benefits that individuals could gain from their social networks, few studies have investigated and found that social capital may not always provide benefits such as job information, employment influence, and getting hired directly by a social tie (e.g. Parks-Yancy et al., 2009; Smith, 2005). For example, Smith (2005) found that some people are unwilling to share their social capital resources with others believing that if the referral did not perform as expected at the job it will jeopardize their own credibility with their employer. In this regard, Parks-Yancy et al., (2009) suggest that this situation could also be true if the referrer him or herself was not held in high regard on the job. Further, although Torres and Huffman (2004) found that social relations help individuals to obtain better-paying jobs than the jobs that they already have, Granovetter (1973) found that some people, who rely on others like friends and family, sometimes find worse jobs rather than better ones. Therefore, scholars (e.g. Adler and Kwon, 2002; Portes, 1998) highlight the need of better understanding the downsides of social capital both for the focal actor and for others.

Second, in the organisational context, social capital is not cost free; it requires maintenance. Job security can be a potential cost of maintaining social capital (Dess and Shaw, 2001; Leana and Van Buren, 1999). It is said that one of the by-products of practices such as downsizing is that individuals will invest less in firm-specific knowledge

and more in knowledge valued by the external labour market, which can damage collective identity (Leana and Van Buren, 1999). Hence, organisations may invest in job security as a means of promoting collective mindedness - a kind of maintenance cost (see Leana and Van Buren, 1999). Based on the above reviewed literature and preliminary investigations made by us on the said industry, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 2: Dimensions of social capital will have a significant positive effect on job search and job security.

Career advancement. Previous research has also shown the importance of social networks within the organisation as well as in different organisational settings for career advancement and greater managerial performance (e.g. Belliveau et al., 1996; Burt, 1992; Lin, 2001; Lin and Huang, 2005; Rodan and Galunic, 2004). Based on an individual's career goals, an individual can build a network of relationships with individuals in one's organisation, profession, and community (Forret and Dougherty, 2004). Because individuals in these three domains are less likely to know one another, it is suggested that they have the ability to provide distinctive benefits (de Janasz and Forret, 2008). For example, Burt (1997) and Forret and Dougherty (2004) found that networks influence individual's promotions and salary progression. Further, Royster (2003) found that the use of social capital resources can help individuals to obtain work-related training opportunities.

Specific literature on information technology (IT) sector suggests that IT professionals have a strong need for growth and personal development compared to professionals in other occupations (Lee, 2002). Further, de Janasz and Forret (2008) suggest that in the era of boundaryless careers, individuals make frequent career moves and social relations have become crucial for enhancing career success. Based on the above reviewed literature and preliminary investigations made by us on the said industry, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 3: Dimensions of social capital will have a significant positive effect on career advancement.

Method

Sample

A random sample of software developers full-time attached to offshore outsourced software development firms was selected. The list of software development firms registered and operate under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) was used as it is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments. Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all the BOI registered firms should export at least 90% of their output. Therefore, the BOI registered software development firms provide at least 90% of their work for offshore client firms. There were about 36 firms engaged purely in software development. A contact person was identified at each firm. This person was asked to randomly identify respondents whose main job function is software development from his/her firm and distribute the link to the on-line survey questionnaire via e-mail (also refer to the section on *methods of data collection*). We sent out 200 questionnaires and 105 valid responses were returned, a response rate of 53% of the original sample.

With regard to demographics of the respondents, 61% were male and 39% were female. All the respondents belonged to the age range of 24 to 32 years. This may be due to the nature of the Sri Lankan offshore software development industry, which is young. All the respondents had Bachelor's degrees; the possession of a Bachelor's degree is the main entry requirement for this profession in offshore outsourced software development sector in Sri Lanka. The mean tenure in the IT industry was 5 years (S.D. = 1.03).

Information regarding population characteristics of software developers in the offshore outsourced software development firms in Sri Lanka is difficult to be found.

When the sample characteristics are compared with the labour force statistics of the country, of the total 7.5 Million labour force of the country, 65% were male. 13% of the labour force belonged to the age group of 15-24 years, 36% belonged to the age group of 25-39 years, and 51% belonged to the age group of over 40 years. With regard to the educational attainment of the labour force, 16% had General Certificate in Education (Ordinary Level) that equals to 10 years of education, and 16% had an educational attainment which is equal or above the level of General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level), which equals to 13 years of education (Department of Census and Statistics, 2008). When the sample characteristics are compared with IT workforce statistics of the country, at the end of 2006 offshore IT outsourcing sector had approximately a 30,000 member IT workforce of which 45% had a Bachelor's degree or a higher qualification in IT (SLICTA, 2007). At the end of 2004, 22 percent of the IT workforce was female, but this is on the increase as in 1998 it was only 17 percent (SLICTA, 2005). Although no specific segregation of data based on the education levels of the IT labour force is available by gender, of the females employed in the country, 22 percent have an educational qualification of General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) or above, compared to a proportion of 13 percent employed males having the same level of education (Department of Census and Statistics, 2005). Overall, the demographics of the sample of our study do not show a deviation from the details of the sample characteristics depicted in the prior independent studies of Wickramasinghe (2009) and SLICTA (2007), where both studies collected data in 2006.

Measures

Dimensions of social capital. The literature suggests that the tools needed to measure social capital at the level of employed individuals are very different from those needed to measure social capital at the level of households, communities, organisations or countries (see Kaasa and Parts, 2008; Lillbacka, 2006). Based on the insight gained from above reviewed literature (such as Kristiansen, 2004; McFadyen and Cannella,

2004) and our preliminary investigations, a 10-item list was developed adhering to the guidelines recommended by Nunnally (1978) (refer to Table 2). The items were pre-tested on a sample that fitted with the intended sample of the study. The items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). For the scale, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and principal components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: Eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al., 2006). The 10-item measure had a reliability of .724. Factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 72% (71.86) of the variance. The item measures, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 2. Factor 1 was labelled as "Social relations", Factor 2 as "Generalised norms", and Factor 3 as the "Degree of trust".

Take in Table 2

Types of networks that individuals call upon, and the nature and extent of their interactions with the members of those networks. Several questions were asked on the number of social relations individuals have, measured by the number of networks an individual is being a member (ratio scale), and the strength of ties, measured by the frequency of interaction between network members (ratio scale) (refer to Table 4 and 5).

Benefits gained from the dimensions of social capital. Based on the insight gained from above reviewed literature (such as Widén-Wulff and Ginman, 2004) and our preliminary investigations, a 10-item list was developed to capture individuals' subjective perceptions of knowledge sharing, job openings and job security, and career advancement as personal benefits associated with the social capital (refer to Table 3).

The items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'strongly disagree' to (5) 'strongly agree'. The 10-item measure had a reliability of .766. principal components factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 86% (85.84) of the variance. The item measures, factor loadings, and reliability statistics are shown in Table 3. Factor 1 was labelled as "Knowledge sharing", Factor 2 as "Job openings and job security" and Factor 3 as "Career progression".

Take in Table 3

Methods of data collection and analysis

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the self-administered survey questionnaire was in English language. Considering the target audience of the study and their capabilities, an on-line questionnaire was developed and distributed the link to the on-line survey via e-mail (also refer to the section on *sample*). As data for both independent and dependent variables were collected from a single source, measures were taken to reduce common method bias. First, a psychological separation of measurement was obtained by creating the on-line questionnaire in such a way that it was in two pages (page one on dimensions and page two on benefits gained) and once the page one is saved, respondents were not allowed to go back to refer to their answers to the "dimensions" when completing the questions on "benefits gained" (refer to Podsakoff et al., 2003). Second, factor analysis was used to examine data; it was observed that a majority of the variance of all the constructs was not accounted for by a single factor (Harman's single-factor test) fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al. (2003).

Data were analysed using multiple regression. Respondents' industry tenure, age, gender, and the size of the firm (in terms of the number of employees) were taken as

control variables. Gender was coded as male=1 and female=0. Respondents' industry tenure, age, the number of employees in the firm, the number of networks an individual is being a member, and the frequency of interaction between network members were assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the values provided by the respondents for each construct.

Results

Table 4 shows the nature of networks that software developers called upon, and the nature and extent of their interactions with the members of those networks. In addition, the number of networks an individual is being a member, and the strength of ties measured by the frequency of interaction between network members are shown in Table 5. Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations between the variables are also shown in Table 5.

Take in Table 4

Take in Table 5

Table 6 shows the results of regression analysis. The results suggest that social relations ($p < .01$), the number of networks ($p < .05$), and the frequency of interaction ($p < .05$), all of which describe the nature of network, and the degree of trust ($p < .01$), which describes the strength of ties, significantly predict knowledge sharing. Social relations ($p < .01$), the number of networks ($p < .01$), and the frequency of interaction ($p < .01$) significantly predict job openings and job security. Social relations ($p < .01$), the number of networks ($p < .05$), the frequency of interaction ($p < .05$), and the degree of trust ($p < .001$) significantly predict career progression. However, generalised norms have not

predicted any of the dependent variables significantly. Overall, hypotheses are partially supported.

Take in Table 6

Discussion and managerial implications

Whilst it is recognised that today's capital has expanded its scope to include social relationships as well, literature provides little empirical evidence on the dimensions of and benefits gained from social capital as manifested in the attitudes and expectations of knowledge workers. Drawing upon a random sample of software developers in Sri Lanka employed by the offshore outsourced software development firms the study examined the relationship between dimensions of social capital and the benefits of knowledge sharing, job openings and job security and career advancement. The novel character of this research is that it brought together and analyzed in parallel several factors which until recently had been analyzed separately.

It was found that software developers belong to networks and maintain interactions with the network members (refer to Table V). They most often interact with people belong to a similar level of educational/professional background (mean=3.61). This is followed by people belong to different levels of skills/expertise (mean=3.39) and different levels of industry experience (mean=3.24). Further, software developers most frequently interact with networks comprise of family members and neighbours (mean=4.07), work colleagues and associates (mean=3.86), and major customers, suppliers, and other key stakeholders (mean=3.85). Furthermore, they make a certain amount of investment in establishing and maintaining relationships (refer to Table IV). In this regard, the literature also suggests that the number of direct exchange partners in a network increases the amount of information, ideas, and resources in it and that the

relationships require time, energy, and attention to establish and maintain (see McFadyen and Cannella, 2004).

The main objective of the study was to investigate the relationship between different dimensions of social capital and the perceived benefits of knowledge sharing, job openings and job security and career advancement. It was found that knowledge sharing is predicted by social relations, the number of networks an individual is being a member, the frequency of interaction between network members and the degree of trust. This finding supports the previous studies that indicated the dimensions of social capital influence knowledge sharing (e.g. Dyer and Chu, 2003; Leana and Van Buren, 1999; Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). For instance, Leana and Van Buren (1999) identify trust as a by-product of successful collective action; workgroups that successfully complete a project are likely to exhibit a higher level of trust, which makes further and more complex collaborative efforts possible. This situation closely fit with the work of software developers because software development is organised around projects and personal networks; people come together to work on a specific project. Some past studies (e.g. Kristiansen, 2004) identify that the number of networks reduces transaction costs and risks and improve learning and information-sharing possibilities.

Job openings and job security is predicted by social relations, the number of networks an individual is being a member, and the frequency of interaction between network members. This finding supports the previous studies that indicated the dimensions of social capital influence accessing job openings (e.g. Forret and Dougherty, 2004; Granovetter 1995; Waters and Smith, 2008) and job security (e.g. Dess and Shaw, 2001; Leana and Van Buren, 1999). For instance, the importance of social networks for the continued development of a technical culture within high-technology sectors has been highly emphasized by Waters and Smith (2008). Further, in an examination of job and geographical mobility among professionals within high-technology sectors, Malecki and Bradbury (1992) suggest that individuals have advantages in moving from one employer to another rather than relying on promotion

within the internal labour market of a single firm. Such a situation depends on individuals' ability to obtain new information about new roles and job opportunities, which they could gain from resources available to them through their organizational positions, elite institutional ties and social networks.

Career progression is predicted by social relations, the number of networks an individual is being a member, the frequency of interaction between network members and the degree of trust. The findings support the previous studies that indicated the dimensions of social capital influence career progression (e.g. Belliveau et al., 1996; Burt, 1997; Maman, 2000). For instance, Burt (1983) suggests that the establishment of social relationships increases with the number of organizations to which an individual is affiliated. Such a situation provides an example for the Matthew effect proposed by Merton (1968) where "to those who have, more will be given". Lee (2002), in the context of IT industry suggests that IT professionals have a strong need for growth and personal development compared to professionals in other occupations. Therefore, the findings suggest that software developers rely on their social capital to enhance their career possibilities.

Norms reflect consensus among the actors in a system of relationships and they provide a motivational basis for social exchange (see Staber, 2006). For instance, norms create openness, motivation and willingness to engage in knowledge sharing (see Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). However, norms have not predicted any of the dependent variables of the study, i.e., knowledge sharing, job openings and job security and career advancement, significantly. This finding implies that the social capital of software developers may not depend on enforceability. A possible explanation for this situation is that the work related experiences of software developers are a product of a common fate and they learn to identify with each other and support each other's initiatives, i.e., moral obligation (refer to Portes, 1998). Therefore, software developers as members of the same community may appropriate altruistic dispositions that could be tapped by other members of the same community (i.e., software development) to obtain privileged

access to benefits of knowledge sharing, job openings and job security and career advancement.

The term social capital was first introduced in community studies to explain how social relationships provide the basis for collective action (e.g. Bourdieu, 1986; Portes, 1998). In the global economy, social capital dimensions such as the number of networks an individual belongs to, the frequency of interactions and the degree of trust among the members of the network cannot be ignored in understanding software developers' attempt to stay technically up-to-date and employed for a longer period of time. The concept of social capital seems ideally suited to investigate a range of benefits that individuals in new occupations in the knowledge era could gain from their social resources. However, so far, there have been only a few studies about the dimensions of and benefits gained from social capital and those studies included a limited number of social capital dimensions and a limited number of benefits in a single empirical study (e.g. Waters and Smith, 2008). The current study attempted to address this gap. Overall, the findings of the study suggest that the dimensions of social capital provide benefits to individuals, i.e., knowledge sharing, job openings and job security and career advancement. Further, as discussed in the above paragraphs, the results also imply that different dimensions of social capital are capable of capturing different benefits that could be gained by individuals. Overall, the findings of our study could be used to explain the effect of social capital at two levels. First, how could individual actors benefit by understanding their social capital. Second, how could firms benefit by understanding their employees' social capital.

Considering the former, i.e., how could individual actors benefit by understanding their social capital, on the one hand, knowledge, skills and abilities gained by software developers from the formal education system as well as their prior work experiences and training help them to become employable. However, individuals in the emerging work environments have to give considerable attention to their social relationships not only to be adaptable and self-directed but also to be employable (see Hall, 2002). On the other

hand, Sri Lankan offshore outsourced software development firms have about two layers in the organisational hierarchy- top management and technical specialists. Previous studies provide evidence that opportunities available for promotion for IT professionals are few and far between (Wickramasinghe, 2009). When vertical career movement is limited and position immobility has become a normal event in the offshore outsourced IT industry, IT professionals have to stay in the same position longer than expected without any reduction in their performance level. Such a circumstance is neither planned nor expected by individuals in the industry. However, they have to react to this very nature of the industry by taking the ownership of their own careers and the responsibility for their own career development and performance. The findings suggest that social relations, the number of networks an individual is being a member and the frequency of interaction between network members have a significant effect on knowledge sharing, searching for and securing employment opportunities, and career advancement while the degree of trust has a significant effect on knowledge sharing and career advancement. Therefore, the findings imply the importance of building and nurturing personal and professional relationships. Further, individuals should be motivated to periodically renew and reconfirm their social bonds to retain efficacy. In this regard, networking could be seen as a critical competency for career and personal success. Overall, our findings add value for academics and practitioners alike in the context of boundaryless work environments, where the burden of responsibility for one's career has shifted from the organisation to the individual (see Hall, 2002).

Considering the latter, i.e., how could firms benefit by understanding their employees' social capital, although social capital is based on the premise that social relations that individuals maintain provide value to its members (see Bourdieu, 1986; Coleman, 1990), when applied to the organisational and inter-organisational level, the social relations that its employees maintain could be identified as an organisation's primary asset and a source of competitive advantage (see Dess and Shaw, 2001; Young, 2005). In the global business environment, social capital facilitates coordination,

knowledge sharing, and innovation (see De Backere and Rappa, 1994; Rodan and Galunic, 2004). In this regard, Staber (2006) argues that “the concept of social capital combines ideas that relate to important processes of cross-cultural management: accessing multiple sources of new knowledge, developing norms and codes that permit individuals and firms to process information, and building trust to facilitate cooperative exchange” (p. 190). In the global outsourcing environment, where organisational structures take on flatter and more decentralised form, putting a premium on social capital becomes beneficial for the firms. Our investigations suggest that individuals maintain a network of relationships with work colleagues as well as with major customers, suppliers, and other key stakeholders. In the global outsourcing environment the most of the major customers, suppliers, and key stakeholders locate in foreign countries. Therefore, it is beneficial for the firms with a long term-view to pay more attention to evolving relationships among individual actors involving internal as well as external community and facilitate them to maintain such relationships. In this regard, de Janasz and Forret (2008) argue that many individuals feel uncomfortable with, or unskilled in, networking. Hence, the role of firms in enhancing their employees’ networking capabilities becomes important. In so doing, firms could develop communities that share knowledge. For instance, firms could make arrangements for employees to meet and spend time with major customers, suppliers, and other key stakeholders located in foreign countries. Further, firms could encourage and support (in financial terms as well as the provision of paid time-offs) for their employees to join and actively participate in professional associations, civic organisations, or become involved in community activities. Alternatively, firms could build diverse collaborative networks with universities/industry associations. Furthermore, when considering the high turnover rate of IT professionals of the Sri Lankan offshore outsourced IT firms (Wickramasinghe, 2009), firms could establish alumni networks of former software developers/IT professionals. All these require firms to have a long-term view of the employment

relationship with its employees, which could in turn contribute to its very survival overtime.

Limitations and future research

With regard to the limitations of the study, first, the size of the sample is small compared to other studies conducted using survey-based techniques. Second, although we have taken steps to minimise common method variance, there are weaknesses in the use of self-reported data in survey research. Third, we have not come across previous empirical survey-based studies that investigated in detail the links proposed in this study. Therefore, the validation of measures used in this study requires an assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Fourth, Bourdieu (1986) as well as Portes (1998) highlight the need of assessing social relations in terms of the amount and quality of the resources. However, such an evaluation is beyond the scope of the current study. Fifth, the current study investigated the dimensions of social capital and the categories of benefits separately. One could argue those are interrelated and serve to reinforce one another. For such an investigation a large sample and more sophisticated data analysis techniques are necessary.

With regard to areas for future research, first, previous researchers suggested that there could be situations where social capital is linked to power relations inhibiting the sharing of knowledge (e.g. Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998; Willem and Scarbrough, 2006). For instance, Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) suggested that interpersonal networks can, in the long-run, produce strong norms and mutual identification among network members limiting openness to new information and diverse views. Willem and Scarbrough (2006) found that the consequences of social capital are ambivalent and unpredictable as social capital represents a source of power and politicking. Hence, future studies could investigate such drawbacks of social capital to understand the challenges behind knowledge sharing.

Second, in the offshore outsourced software development sector networks become global. Such global networks comprise of members from different cultural backgrounds. Therefore, cultural variables could be added to investigate whether cultural differences between network members (in the international context) act as a constraint or an opportunity in enhancing individuals' social capital.

Third, Portes (1998) suggested that interpersonal networks could, over time, produce strong norms and mutual identification among network members thus limiting openness to new information and diverse views. In a similar vein, McFadyen and Cannella (2004) argue that although the number of an individual's relations positively affects knowledge creation, the association is not strictly linear. They suggest that establishing and maintaining relationships begins to cut into the time available for the solo activities that are also critical to knowledge creation—such as reading and running experiments. Hence, future research of longitudinal in nature would be beneficial.

Fourth, Maman (2000) argues that social capital is rendered obsolete by contextual changes. For example, a combination of individual and structural features could determine career progression of individuals. Therefore, future research could investigate the role of national business system in this regard.

Finally, the current study investigated social capital as an individual characteristic. In this regard, Payne et al. (2010) suggest the need of viewing social capital through a multilevel lens in which individual and collective behaviours could occur and how these behaviours could influence the nested levels of social organization (i.e., individuals within teams within organizations within industries). Therefore, these all open the door for further investigations.

References

Adam, F. (2008), "Mapping social capital across Europe: findings, trends and methodological shortcomings of cross-national surveys", *Social Science Information*, Vol. 47 No. 2, 159-186.

- Adler, P.S. and Kwon, S-W. (2002), "Social capital: prospect for a new concept", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 17-40.
- Baker, W.E. (1990), "Market networks and corporate behaviour", *American Journal of Sociology*, Vol. 96, pp. 589-625.
- Belliveau, M., O'Reilly, C. and Wade, J. (1996), "Social capital at the top: effects of social similarity and status on CEO compensation", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 39, pp. 1568-1593.
- Bourdieu, P. (1986), "The forms of capital". In J. G. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education*. pp.241-258. New York: Greenwood.
- Bueno, E., Salmador, M.P. and Rodríguez, O. (2004), "The role of social capital in today's economy: empirical evidence and proposal of a new model of intellectual capital", *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, Vol. 5 No. 4, pp. 556-574.
- Burgoon, J. K., Bonito, J. A., Ramirez, Jr. A., Dunbar, N. E., Kam, K. and Fischer, J. (2002), "Testing the interactivity principle: effects of mediation, propinquity, and verbal and nonverbal modalities in interpersonal interaction," *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 52 No.3, pp.657-677.
- Burt, R.S. (1992), *Structural holes: the social structure of competition*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Burt, R.S. (1997), "A note on social capital and network content", *Social Networks*, Vol. 19, pp. 355-373.
- Burt, R.S. (1983), *Corporate profits and cooptation: networks of market constraints and directorate ties in the American economy*. New York: Academic Press.
- Coleman, J. (1990), *Foundations of social theory*. Boston: Harvard University Press.
- Crudeli, L., Macinelli, S. and Ponti, G. (2008), "Social capital or economic rents? an experimental study", *Rationality and Society*, Vol. 20 No. 3, pp. 311–342.
- De Backere, K. and Rappa, M. (1994), "Technological Communities and the diffusion of knowledge: a replication and validation", *R&D Management*, Vol. 24 No.4, pp. 355–371.

de Janasz, S.C. and Forret, M.L. (2008), "Learning the art of networking: a critical skill for enhancing social capital and career success", *Journal of Management Education*, Vol. 32 No. 5, pp. 629-650.

Department of Census and Statistics (2005), *Bulletin of Labour Force Statistics of Sri Lanka – August 2005*, Available at: www.statistics.gov.lk. Accessed on 26th May 2010.

Department of Census and Statistics (2008), *Sri Lanka Labour Force Survey Final Report - 2007*, Available at: www.statistics.gov.lk. Accessed on 26th May 2010.

Dess, G.G. and Shaw, I.D. (2001), "Voluntary turnover, social capital and organizational performance", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 26 No. 3, pp. 446-456.

Dyer, J.H. and Chu, W. (2003), "The role of trustworthiness in reducing transaction costs and improving performance: empirical evidence from the United States, Japan, and Korea". *Organization Science*, Vol.14, pp. 57–68.

Forret, M.L. and Dougherty, T.W. (2004), "Networking behaviors and career outcomes: differences for men and women?", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 25, pp. 419-437.

Fukuyama, F. (1995), *Trust: the social virtues and the creation of prosperity*. New York: Free Press.

Granovetter, M. (1973), "The strength of weak ties", *American Journal of Sociology*, Vol. 78 No. 6, pp. 1360–1380.

Granovetter, M.S. (1995), *Getting a job: a study of contacts and careers* (2nd ed.). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Hair, J.F.Jr, Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E., Tatham, R.L., (2006), *Multivariate Data Analysis*, (6 ed). India, Pearson Education.

Hall, D.T. (2002), *Careers in and out of organizations*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Hislop, D. (2005), "The effect of network size on intra-network knowledge processes", *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, Vol. 3, pp. 244–252.

Inkpen, A.C. and Tsang, E.W.K. (2005), "Social capital, networks, and knowledge transfer", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 30, No. 1, pp. 146–165.

- Jarvenpaa, S.L. and Mao, J-Y. (2008), "Operational capabilities development in mediated offshore software services models", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 23, pp. 3–17.
- Kaasa, A. and Parts, E. (2008), "Individual-level determinants of social capital in Europe: differences between country groups", *Acta Sociologica*, Vol. 51 No. 2, pp. 145–168.
- Khan, S.R. (2006), "Learning from South Asian 'successes': tapping social capital", *South Asia Economic Journal*, Vol. 7 No.2, pp. 157-178.
- Krackhardt, D. (1990), "Assessing the political landscape: structure, cognition, and power in organizations", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 35, pp. 342-369.
- Kristiansen, S. (2004), "Social networks and business success: the role of subcultures in an African context", *The American Journal of Economics and Sociology*, Vol. 63 No. 5, pp. 1149-1171.
- Leana, C.R., and Van Buren, H. J., III. (1999), "Organizational social capital and employment practices", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 24 No.3, pp. 538-555.
- Lee, P.C.B. (2002), "Career goals and career management strategy among information technology professionals", *Career Development International*, Vol. 7 No. 1, 6-13
- Lillbacka, R. (2006), "*Measuring social capital: assessing construct stability of various operationalizations of social capital in a Finnish sample*", *Acta Sociologica*, Vol. 49 No. 2, pp. 201–220.
- Lin, N. (1999), "Building a theory of social capital", *Connection*, Vol. 22, pp. 28–51.
- Lin, N. (2001), *Social capital: a theory of social structure and action*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Lin, S-C. and Huang, Y.M. (2005), "The role of social capital in the relationship between human capital and career mobility: Moderator or mediator?", *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 191-205.
- Mahnke, V., Wareham, J. and Bjorn-Andersen, N. (2008), "Offshore middlemen: transnational intermediation in technology sourcing", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 23, pp. 18–30.

- Malecki, E.J. and Bradbury, S.L. (1992), "R&D facilities and professional labour: labour force dynamics in high technology", *Regional Studies*, Vol. 26 No. 2, pp.123–136.
- Maman, D. (2000), "Who accumulates directorships of big business firms in Israel?: organizational structure, social capital and human capital", *Human Relations*, Vol. 53 No. 5, pp. 603–629.
- McFadyen, M.A. and Cannella, A.A.Jr. (2004), "Social capital and knowledge creation: diminishing returns of the number and strength of exchange relationships", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 47 No. 5, pp. 735–746.
- Merton, K.R. (1968), "The Matthew effect in science: the reward and communication system of science are considered", *Science*, Vol. 159, pp. 56–63.
- Nahapiet, J. and Ghoshal, S. (1998), "Social capital, intellectual capital, and the organizational advantage", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 23, pp. 242-266.
- Nunnally, J.C. (1978), *Psychometric Theory*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Parks-Yancy, R., DiTomaso, N. and Post, C. (2009), "How does tie strength affect access to social capital resources for the careers of working and middle class African-Americans?", *Critical Sociology*, Vol. 35 No. 4, pp. 541–563
- Payne, G.T., Moore, C.B., Griffis, S.E. and Autry, C.W. (2010), "Multilevel challenges and opportunities in social capital research", *Critical Sociology*, Advanced online publication, DOI: 10.1177/0149206310372413
- Podsakoff, P., MacKenzie, S., Lee, J-Y. and Podsakoff, N., (2003), "Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 88 No. 5, pp. 879-903.
- Portes, A. (1998), "Social capital: its origins and applications in contemporary sociology", *Annual Review of Sociology*, Vol. 24, pp. 1-24.
- Portes, A. and Sensenbrenner, J. (1993), "Embeddedness and immigration: notes on the social determinants of economic action", *American Journal of Sociology*, Vol. 98, pp. 1320-1350.
- Putnam, R. (1993), "The prosperous community: social capital and public life", *The American Prospect*, Vol. 13, pp. 35-42.

- Putnam, R. (2000), *Bowling alone: the collapse and revival of American community*. New York: Simon and Schuster.
- Rodan, S. and Galunic, C. (2004), "More than network structure: how knowledge heterogeneity influences managerial performance and innovativeness", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 25, pp. 541-562.
- Rottman, J.W. (2008), "Successful knowledge transfer within offshore supplier networks: a case study exploring social capital in strategic alliances", *Journal of Information Technology*, Vol. 23, pp. 31–43.
- Royster, D.A. (2003), *Race and the Invisible Hand: How White Networks Exclude Black Men from Blue-Collar Jobs*. University of California Press: Los Angeles.
- Scholarios, D. and Marks, A. (2004), "Work-life balance and the software worker", *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 54-74.
- SLICTA (2005), *Geared for Growth: The Improving Stability of the Sri Lankan IT Workforce: National IT Workforce Survey 2005*, Sri Lanka ICT Association, Colombo.
- SLICTA (2007), *Rising Demand: The Increasing Demand for IT Workers Spells a Challenging Opportunity for the IT Industry-National IT Workforce Survey*, Sri Lanka ICT Association, Colombo.
- Smith, S.S. (2005), "Don't put my name on it': social capital activation and job-finding assistance among the Black Urban Poor", *American Journal of Sociology*, Vol. 111 No. 2, pp. 1–57.
- Staber, U. (2006), "Social capital processes in cross cultural management", *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 189-203.
- Torres, L. and Huffman, M.L. (2004), "Who benefits? Gender differences in returns to social network diversity", In DiTomaso, N. and Post, C. (eds) *Diversity in the Workforce*, pp. 60–101. Elsevier Jai: London.
- Tymon, W.G. and Stumpf, S.A. (2003), "Social capital in the success of knowledge workers", *Career Development International*, Vol. 8 No. 1, pp. 12-20.
- Waters, R. and Smith, H.L. (2008), "Social networks in high-technology local economies: the cases of Oxfordshire and Cambridgeshire", *European Urban and Regional Studies*, Vol. 15 No. 1, pp. 21-37.

Wickramasinghe, V. (2009), "Predictors of job satisfaction among IT graduates in offshore outsourced IT firms", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 413-431.

Widén-Wulff, G. and Ginman, M. (2004), "Explaining knowledge sharing in organizations through the dimensions of social capital", *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 30 No. 5, pp. 448-458.

Willem, A. and Scarbrough, H. (2006), "Social capital and political bias in knowledge sharing: an exploratory study", *Human Relations*, Vol. 59 No. 10, pp. 1343.

Wu, W-P. (2008), "Dimensions of social capital and firm competitiveness improvement: the mediating role of information sharing", *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 45 No.1, pp. 122-146.

Young, C-S. (2005), "Top management teams' social capital in Taiwan: the impact on firm value in an emerging economy", *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 177-190.

Tables

Table 1: Social capital definitions (a selection)

Author(s)	Definition	Treatment of social capital
Baker (1990)	"a resource that actors derive from specific social structures and then use to pursue their interests; it is created by changes in the relationship among actors" (p. 619).	private good
Belliveau et al.(1996)	"an individual's personal network and elite institutional affiliations" (p. 1572).	private good
Bourdieu (1986)	"the aggregate of the actual or potential resources which are linked to possession of a durable network of more or less institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance or recognition" (p. 248).	private good
Burt, 1992	"friends, colleagues, and more general contacts through whom you receive opportunities to use your financial and human capital" (p. 9).	private good
Coleman (1990)	"Social capital is defined by its function. It is not a single entity, but a variety of different entities having two characteristics' in common: They all consist of some aspect of social structure, and they facilitate certain actions of individuals who are within the structure" (p. 302).	public goods
Fukuyama (1995)	"the ability of people to work together for common purposes in groups and organizations" (p. 10).	public goods
Inkpen and Tsang (2005)	"the aggregate of resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or organization—a definition that accommodates both the private and public good perspectives of social capital" (p. 151).	private and public good
Leana and Van Buren (1999)	"a resource reflecting the character of social relations within the firm. Organizational social capital is realized through members' levels of collective goal orientation and shared trust, which create value by facilitating successful collective action. Organizational social capital is an asset that can benefit both the organization (e.g., creating value for shareholders) and its members who have an employment relationship with the firm (e.g., enhancing employee skills)" (p. 538).	private and public good
Lin (2001)	"Social capital may be defined operationally as the resources embedded in social networks accessed and used by actors for actions . . . and social capital can also be envisioned as investment by individuals in interpersonal relationships useful in the markets" (p. 25).	private good
Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998)	"the sum of the actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or social unit. Social capital thus comprises both the network and the assets that may be mobilized through that network" (p. 243)	public good
Portes and Sensenbrenner (1993)	"those expectations for action within a collectivity that affect the economic goals and goal seeking behavior of its members, even if these expectations are not oriented toward the economic sphere" (p. 1323).	private good
Putnam (2000)	"features of social organisation such as networks, norms, and social trust that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit" (p. 67).	public goods
Wu, 2008	"the features that are embedded in social organizations such as network ties, norms, and trust that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit" (p. 125).	public good

Table 2: Dimensions of social capital

	Factor 1: Social relations	Factor 2: Generalised norms	Factor 3: Degree of trust
I have close relationships with many network members	.872		
I actively participate in voluntary activities	.851		
I involve in professional organizations	.796		
I have established good working relationships with my organisational members	.785		
Most of my network members willing to engage in collective action for mutual benefit		.766	
Most of my network members willing to co-operate for mutual benefit		.714	
Most of the time my network members try to be helpful		.702	
Most people with whom I have contact can be trusted			.783
My network members do not act opportunistically			.721
Most of my network members try to be fair			.718
Explained variation	35.84%	21.10%	14.92%
Eigenvalue	2.54	2.12	1.98
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.847	.742	.703

Table 3: Benefits gained

	Factor 1: Knowledge sharing	Factor 2: Job openings and job security	Factor 3: Career progression
I can gain access to knowledge that is helpful in mastering job tasks from my network members	.856		
I receive information about innovations in my field from my network members, timely	.823		
I share useful new knowledge that I acquired among my network members	.801		
I receive information about job opportunities from my network members		.825	
My network members are helpful in job search		.810	
The relationships that I maintain with my network members help me to secure employment opportunities		.766	
My present workplace assure job security to promote mindedness		.716	
Contacts that I have established are essential for my career success			.796
The relationships that I maintain are helpful in making career moves			.745
The relationships that I maintain are helpful in salary progression			.723
Explained variation	40.39%	26.12%	19.33%
Eigenvalue	3.34	2.62	1.18
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.815	.777	.764

Table 4: Type and nature of networks

	Mean	SD
Nature of people frequently interact with:		
Similar level of educational/professional background	3.61	1.01
Different levels of skills/expertise	3.39	.98
Different levels of industry experience	3.24	1.06
Similar career objectives	3.10	.92
Same sex	2.41	1.03
Type of networks frequently interact with:		
Family members and neighbours	4.07	1.03
Work colleagues and associates	3.86	.80
Major customers, suppliers, and other key stakeholders	3.85	1.12
Members from professional associations	2.72	1.04
Friends from school, university, etc.	2.60	.91
Members from community groups	2.56	1.16
Monthly total contribution (if any) for the networks belonged to (in Sri Lankan Rupees*):		
Less than Rs.1000	57	
Between Rs.1000-5000	33	
More than Rs.5000	10	

Note: *1 US\$ = 110 Sri Lankan rupees (as of November 2010).

Table 5: Descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Gender ^a	.61	.49	1										
2 Age ^b	3.31	.06	.071	1									
3 Tenure ^b	2.24	.44	.072	.283*	1								
4 No. of employees in the firm ^b	5.81	1.12	.024	.170	.168	1							
5 Frequency of interaction ^b	6.12	.62	.062	.148	.030	.075	1						
6 No. of networks ^b	2.36	.82	.030	.183	.202*	.114	.207*	1					
7 Social relations	3.57	.56	.273**	.064	.082	.182	.062	.075	1				
8 Generalized norms	3.23	.81	.042	.153	.043	.013	.157	.171	.185	1			
9 Degree of trust	3.56	.70	.155	.132	.019	.113	.181	.070	.198	.026	1		
10 Knowledge sharing	3.50	.82	.074	.123	.090	.137	.214*	.241*	.440**	.027	.494**	1	
11 Job openings and job security	3.80	.60	.133	.096	.056	.108	.275*	.279*	.456**	.118	.195	.184	1
12 Career progression	3.75	.78	.077	.190	.070	.022	.270*	.252*	.394**	.054	.564**	.167	.156

Notes: ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

^a Binary-coded variables.

^b Log transformed

Table 6: Results of regression analysis

	Knowledge sharing (β)	Job openings and job security (β)	Career progression (β)
Gender	.033	.111	.042
Age	.156	.132	.088
Tenure	.122	.026	.062
No. of employees in the firm	.074	.064	.031
Frequency of interaction	.228*	.298**	.214*
No. of networks	.244*	.274**	.189*
Social networks	.356**	.360**	.302**
Generalized norms	.093	.063	.055
Degree of trust	.314**	.099	.433***
Model R^2 (Adj.)	.265***	.232***	.357***

Notes: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.